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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Joint pain is a common complaint among patients presenting to hospitals. Knee pain, in particular, may arise from various etiologies, including degenerative joint diseases, infections, rheumatologic, and hematologic disorders. This case report discusses a rare cause of joint pain: Tenosynovial Giant Cell Tumor (TGCT).

Case Presentation: A 43-year-old male patient diagnosed with TGCT, a condition with an incidence of 9.2 per million in the United States, presented to the hospital for the first time due to complaints that had persisted for approximately three years (Heijden et al., 2012). As the initial magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) could not establish a definitive diagnosis despite symptoms of swelling and pain, the patient sought repeated consultations from different specialties.

Discussion: Finally, upon presenting to our clinic, a thorough clinical evaluation and imaging assessment suggested a preliminary diagnosis of TGCT, prompting the decision for surgical intervention. During arthroscopic surgery, characteristic findings of TGCT were identified, and the biopsy results confirmed the preliminary diagnosis (Fang & Zhang, 2020). Following the debridement procedure, a significant improvement in the patient's symptoms was observed.

Conclusion: Through meticulous physical examination, detailed medical history assessment, and comprehensive imaging studies, an accurate diagnosis was established at the patient's initial visit to our clinic, allowing for timely treatment. Consequently, even in the context of a rare disease, unnecessary diagnostic tests and repeated consultations were avoided, ensuring an efficient allocation of resources and a cost-effective treatment process.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Tenosynovial, knee, knee pain, tenosynovial giant cell tumor

INTRODUCTION

Tenosynovial Giant Cell Tumor (TGCT) is a locally aggressive neoplastic synovial disease that occurs in the synovium, tendon sheath, and bursal structures. Although the exact etiology is not fully understood, it is believed to be caused by reactive inflammatory processes (Arkun, 2014). Extra-articular involvement of the tendon sheath is pathologically equivalent to giant cell tumor. The disease is characterized by synovitis, joint effusions, synovial hypertrophy, and bone erosions (Triplet & O'Donnell, 2025). It typically begins as a small focal mass in the synovium and can grow to involve the entire joint. It is most commonly observed in individuals aged 30-40 years and occurs equally in both men and women. Although rare, the incidence in the United States is 9.2 per million (Heijden et al., 2012). The knee is the most frequently affected joint, but the hip, ankle, shoulder, and elbow may also be involved. The disease usually affects a single joint. Initially presenting with swelling, it may progress to include pain, functional loss, and other symptoms over time (Ottaviani et al., 2011). In addition to clinical findings, diagnostic arthroscopy and pathological evaluation are crucial for diagnosis. Treatment options include both surgical and non-surgical methods. Asymptomatic patients may be monitored. Non-surgical treatment options include CSF-1 receptor antagonists (Aurégan et al., 2014). Surgical intervention may involve partial or total synovectomy (Fang & Zhang, 2020). Additionally, adjuvant radiotherapy may reduce recurrence rates (Aurégan et al., 2014). However, the disease may recur even after complete synovectomy (Heijden et al., 2012). A complication of the disease may be joint destruction, which could require arthroplasty or arthrodesis. In this article, we present a case of a patient who had symptoms for approximately three years and sought care from multiple specialists (Figures 1-4).

Figure 1
2022 Axial

Figure 2
2025 Axial

Figure 3
2022 Sagittal

Figure 4
2025 Sagittal

CASE PRESENTATION

A patient presented to our clinic with recurrent swelling and pain in the left knee. The patient's history revealed that the knee had undergone several aspirations due to similar symptoms and intra-articular hyaluronic acid injections were administered at two different time points. Three years ago, the patient had presented with similar symptoms but was not diagnosed and had also consulted physical therapy and rheumatology clinics. Upon presentation to our clinic, the patient not only had swelling and pain but also experienced functional loss. The range of motion in the knee joint was restricted to 30 degrees in flexion and 15 degrees in extension. MRI imaging was evaluated as suggestive of Tenosynovial Giant Cell Tumor (PVNS) (Triplet & O'Donnell, 2025). The intraoperative findings obtained through arthroscopic debridement and excision supported the diagnosis, and pathological examination confirmed it (Fang & Zhang, 2020) (Figures 5 and 6). After total synovectomy, the patient's pain and swelling symptoms disappeared, functional recovery was achieved, and the range of motion returned to normal. During the three-month follow-up period, the patient's overall

condition remained good, and the patient is being monitored due to the possibility of recurrence, as seen in late-stage cases (Fang & Zhang, 2020).

Figure 5
Intraoperative imaging

Figure 6
Intraoperative imaging

DISCUSSION

At the patient's initial presentation to our clinic, a preliminary diagnosis of Tenosynovial Giant Cell Tumor (TGCT) was established. The patient, who was found to have the diffuse form of TGCT, underwent a total synovectomy via arthroscopic surgery. According to Fang and Zhang, although the outcomes of arthroscopic and open surgical techniques are similar, the recurrence rate in the diffuse form is higher compared to the localized form (Fang & Zhang, 2020). Poutoglidou et al. reported that the diagnosis of the disease is often delayed by an average of five years (Poutoglidou et al., 2020). In the present case, the diagnosis could be established three years after the onset of symptoms. Fang and Zhang also stated that histopathological examination is the gold standard for definitive diagnosis. In our patient, the diagnosis of Tenosynovial Giant Cell Tumor was confirmed by a biopsy sample obtained intraoperatively.

Tenosynovial Giant Cell Tumor must be considered in the differential diagnosis of patients with chronic joint swelling and pain. Increasing awareness of Tenosynovial Giant Cell Tumor can facilitate the diagnosis and treatment process; early diagnosis can help avoid unnecessary imaging techniques and specialist consultations, leading to a cost-effective treatment approach (Fang & Zhang, 2020).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial or personal conflict of interest in this matter.

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